

COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE STRUCTURE OF THE PANCREAS WITH DIFFERENT GLUCOSE TOLERANCE

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Abstract. The purpose of the study was to study the organization of the exocrine and endocrine parts of the pancreas in animals with normal and impaired glucose tolerance. The results were obtained after studying the pancreas of outbred male dogs aged 3-4 years; the structural features of the organ in animals with normal and impaired glucose tolerance were determined at the organ, tissue, cellular and subcellular levels. Specific features of the organization of the exocrine and endocrine parts of the gland in a state of prediabetes are highlighted.

Keywords: impaired glucose tolerance, pancreas, periinsullar exocrinocytes, insulocytes.

INTRODUCTION

According to the Diabetic Association, impaired glucose tolerance is considered an endocrine disorder that precedes the development of type II diabetes mellitus. It is known that as a result of the complex interaction of carbohydrate metabolism reactions in the body, a relatively constant level of glucose in the circulating blood is maintained, which ensures the normal functioning of organs and tissues [1. A significant role in maintaining the dynamic balance between the processes of formation and utilization of glucose belongs to hormonal regulation, including the pancreatic hormones insulin and glucanone [2.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials and methods of research. The experiment was carried out on outbred male dogs 3-4 years old. Typing of animals and the formation of two groups with normal (group I) and impaired (group II) glucose tolerance were carried out using a standard glucose tolerance test and "fasting" blood glucose level according to generally accepted criteria. The state of carbohydrate metabolism was determined by indicators of glucose, insulin, pyruvate and lactate in venous blood.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphometric indicators were obtained using the Image Tools 3.0 program and the MAKS-1005 image analysis installation [3.

The study made it possible to identify specific features of the morphological organization of the pancreas of dogs aged 3-4 years, who are in the same conditions of detention and have an identical diet, depending on the state of carbohydrate metabolism. With altered glucose metabolism, carbohydrate metabolism is characterized by an increased glucose content by 20.4%, pyruvate by 9.7%, and lower blood insulin concentrations by 33.3% (Fig. 1). The data obtained, together with the results of correlation analysis, which determines strong positive relationships between glucose and pyruvate ($r = 0.782$) and insulin and lactate ($r = 0.843$), indicate the predominance of the glycolytic pathway of metabolism in the body low, but the degree of glucose utilization and glycolytic activity are reduced. Similar results were described by A.V. Dreval, I.V. Misnikova, I.A. Barsukov after examining patients with impaired glucose tolerance and impaired fasting glycemia [4].

Fig. 1. Percentage difference in carbohydrate metabolism parameters in animals with normal (group I) and impaired (group II) glucose tolerance.

Upon external examination, the gland has no obvious differences: it has an elongated ribbon-like shape, moderate blood supply, has three lobes, three parts, but the relative mass of the gland (weight index) is 20% less than in animals of the first group.

When studying the gland at the tissue level in animals with a predisposition to diabetes, the relative volume of the exocrine part is less than the values of the first group by 11%, the endocrine part is more by 11.1%, the Richardson/Young index is higher by 24.8%. According to G.G. Avtandilov [1], the index of the ratio of the volumes of the exocrine and endocrine parts (Richardson/Young coefficient) and the “functional index” (the quantitative

ratio of insulinocytes and glucagonocytes) allows one to assess the functional state of each part.

According to the results of quantitative analysis, the number of pancreatic islets exceeds the values of the first group by 10.7%. The parenchyma is dominated by islets of medium and small sizes, some of which consist primarily of insulinocytes. A similar reaction (an increase in the number of islets, a decrease in their mass, and a decrease in insulin secretion) was noted in experimental studies after repeated administration of various doses of glucose to rats [5]. A significant difference in the number of islet cells was also established: there are 11.6% fewer insulinocytes in the islet of dogs in this group, and 11.3% fewer glucagonocytes. The relative volume of insulinocytes is significantly less than the values of the first group by 13.8%.

CONCLUSION

Our study made it possible to formulate specific features of the organization of the pancreas at the organ, tissue, cellular and ultrastructural levels in a state of impaired glucose tolerance, or in the preclinical stage of diabetes mellitus:

- iron has a smaller mass and weight index;
- the relative volume of the endocrine part and the Richardson/Young index are increased;
- in the parenchyma of the “tail part of the gland”, islands of medium and small sizes predominate;
- there are small islets consisting mainly of insulinocytes;
- near the islets in the exocrine parenchyma, the number of acino-islet cells is increased, in the cytoplasm of which, along with zymogenic ones, secretory β -granules are detected.

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